

THE EVOLUTION OF ENGLISH LANGUAGE EDUCATION IN UZBEKISTAN

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Abstract: This article examines the evolution of English language education in Uzbekistan since the country's independence in 1991. Despite progress, challenges such as a shortage of qualified teachers, limited resources, and varying English proficiency levels among learners persist. The article concludes with recommendations for further enhancing English language education in Uzbekistan through teacher training, curriculum development, and increased investment in educational resources and infrastructure.

Keywords: English language education, Uzbekistan, language policy, communicative language teaching, teacher training

Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada 1991-yilda mamlakat mustaqillikka erishganidan beri O'zbekistonda ingliz tilida ta'lim evolyutsiyasi ko'rib chiqilgan. Erishilgan yutuqlarga qaramay, malakali o'qituvchilarning yetishmasligi, cheklangan resurslar va talabalar o'rtasida ingliz tilini bilishning turli darajalari kabi muammolar davom etmoqda. Maqola o'qituvchilarni tayyorlash, o'quv dasturlarini ishlab chiqish va ta'lim resurslari va infratuzilmasiga investitsiyalarni ko'paytirish orqali O'zbekistonda ingliz tilida ta'limni yanada takomillashtirish bo'yicha tavsiyalar bilan yakunlanadi.

Kalit so'zlar: ingliz tilidagi ta'lim, O'zbekiston, til siyosati, kommunikativ tilni o'qitish, o'qituvchilarni tayyorlash

Аннотация: В данной статье рассматривается эволюция образования на английском языке в Узбекистане с момента обретения страной независимости в 1991 году. Несмотря на достигнутый прогресс, сохраняются такие проблемы, как нехватка квалифицированных преподавателей, ограниченные ресурсы и разный уровень владения английским языком среди учащихся. Статья завершается рекомендациями по дальнейшему совершенствованию образования на английском языке в Узбекистане посредством подготовки учителей, разработки учебных программ и увеличения инвестиций в образовательные ресурсы и инфраструктуру.

Ключевые слова: Образование на английском языке, Узбекистан, языковая политика, коммуникативное обучение языку, подготовка учителей

INTRODUCTION

Since gaining independence in 1991, Uzbekistan has undergone significant changes in its education system, particularly in the area of foreign language learning. English has emerged as the most widely taught foreign language, replacing Russian which had dominated during the Soviet era [1]. The Uzbek government has recognized the importance of English proficiency for the country's economic development, international relations, and global competitiveness [2]. This article aims to examine the evolution of English language education in Uzbekistan over the past three decades, focusing on key policies, practices, and outcomes in public schools, higher education institutions, and private language centers.

METHODS AND LITERATURE REVIEW

The article employs a qualitative research approach, conducting a thorough review of existing literature on English language education in Uzbekistan. Key sources include academic journals, government reports, policy documents, and international organization publications [3]. The literature review covers language policy and planning, English in public schools and higher education, and the role of private language centers in Uzbekistan.

RESULTS

The literature review reveals several key findings regarding the evolution of English language education in Uzbekistan:

Shift from Russian to English. Since independence, there has been a significant shift from Russian to English as the dominant foreign language in Uzbekistan's education system [1]. This change reflects the government's recognition of English as a global language and its importance for the country's economic and international relations.

Increasing emphasis on communicative language teaching. English language teaching in Uzbekistan has gradually moved towards communicative language teaching approaches, aiming to develop learners' practical English communication skills [4]. However, the implementation of communicative approaches varies across educational institutions and is often hindered by teachers' limited English proficiency and training [5].

Growing access to English learning resources. The availability of English learning resources, such as textbooks, audio-visual materials, and online

courses, has increased significantly in Uzbekistan over the past decades [6]. However, access to these resources remains uneven, particularly in rural areas and less affluent schools.

Expanding international education opportunities. Uzbekistan has sought to expand international education opportunities for its students and teachers, particularly in English-speaking countries [7]. However, these opportunities are highly competitive and often limited to a small number of high-achieving students and teachers.

ANALYSIS AND DISCUSSION

The Resolution of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. 312 "On measures to effectively organize the popularization of learning foreign languages", adopted on May 19, 2021, aims to further improve the system of learning and teaching foreign languages and bring it to a qualitatively new level [8].

The resolution sets out important measures for the preschool, general secondary, and higher education systems, as well as for the popularization of learning foreign languages. In particular, it provides for improving the educational and methodological support for teaching foreign languages to preschool children, training pedagogical personnel, professional development, and their financial incentives.

In general secondary education, practical steps have been outlined, such as establishing new schools specializing in teaching foreign languages and affiliating them with higher education institutions, introducing an international certification system for school students and teachers, and improving educational literature in line with modern requirements. The resolution envisages a comprehensive set of measures to radically improve the quality of foreign language teaching in the higher education system, expand international cooperation, promote research and academic mobility, and strengthen the capacity of the teaching staff.

The evolution of English language education in Uzbekistan has been shaped by various factors, including government policies, socio-economic conditions, and global trends. However, the implementation of effective English language education in Uzbekistan faces several challenges. One major issue is the shortage of qualified English teachers, particularly in rural areas [5]. Another challenge is the varying levels of English proficiency among learners, which can hinder the effectiveness of classroom instruction. Addressing these inequalities requires a

more equitable distribution of educational resources and targeted support for disadvantaged learners.

CONCLUSIONS

The evolution of English language education in Uzbekistan over the past three decades reflects the country's efforts to embrace English as a tool for international engagement and economic development. Significant progress has been made in terms of language policy, curriculum development, and access to learning resources. However, challenges such as teacher quality, unequal access to education, and varying proficiency levels among learners persist.

To further enhance English language education in Uzbekistan, recommendations include investing in teacher training programs, developing high-quality learning materials, promoting technology and online learning, strengthening international partnerships, and conducting regular assessments and research to inform future decision-making.

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